

SCHOOL HEAD CONFLICT RESOLUTION TECHNIQUES AND MANAGEMENT STYLES FOR IMPROVED TEACHER'S PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

Using descriptive correlational design of research and convenience sampling techniques 100 public elementary teachers of Sto. Angel District, Division of San Pablo City School, during the academic year 2020-2021 was involved as the respondent of the study. The researcher constructed a self-made survey questionnaire with the guidance of the adviser and several knowledgeable persons and made ready for administration to the respondents after the validation through Google Forms. Mean, Standard Deviation and Pearson Product Moment Correlation were employed to analyze the data that gathered from the respondents. Results revealed that out of 100 teacher-respondents, majority are 46 and above, female, married, BS with MA units, Teacher I and with experience of 10 years and above. The results revealed that there is a significant relationship between respondents' perceptions on conflict resolution techniques and teacher's performance. It implies that competing, accommodating, avoiding, collaborating, and compromising of the school heads affect the content knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment and diversity of learners, curriculum and planning, assessment and reporting, and plus factor. Likewise, there is a significant relationship between the respondents' perceptions on management styles and teacher's performance. Therefore, the management styles of the school heads namely, directive, authoritative, affiliative, participative, and pacesetting contribute in strengthening the teacher's performance of public elementary school teachers in schools in Sto. Angel District.

Keywords: conflict resolution techniques, management styles and teacher's performance